

Torsional and Modal Analysis of Automobile Drive Shaft With Different Materials

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ABSTRACT

The current work deals with the study of characteristics of drive shaft to substitute its material with composite material. Suitability of material is analysed by evaluating and comparing shear stress distribution with in the shaft since torsional strength is directly proportional to shear stress and also compared natural frequencies of the drive shaft. The remarkable properties of Composite materials such as high specific stiffness and strength made to consider replacement of drive shaft. Glass and carbon fibres are most extensively using in commercial applications as its easy availability and stability and reliability. Composite material with 5 plies is considered for analysis and analysis is performed by using commercial FEA software ANSYS. Analysis results are indicating that carbon epoxy material is more reliable than glass epoxy material of same physical dimensions with same number plies and stacking sequence and it evident from displacement, shear stress distribution and natural frequencies.

Keyword: Composite, Drive Shaft, Staking sequence, Modal Analysis, FEA.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid Technological Advances in Engineering Design Field result in finding the alternate solution for the conventional materials. The design engineers brought to a point to finding the materials which are more reliable than conventional materials. Researchers and designers are constantly looking for the solutions to provide stronger and durable materials which will answer the needs of fellow engineers. Drive shafts are used as power transmission tubing in many applications, including cooling towers, pumping sets, aerospace, trucks and automobiles. In the design of metallic shaft, knowing the torque and the allowable shear stress for the material, the size of the shaft's cross section can be determined. In the today's days there is a heavy requirement for light weight materials vehicle. The conventional steel material is replaceable by advanced composite materials. Composite materials are favored by most of the scientist in the design of automobiles due to its higher specific strength and stiffness. Wee ton et al. stated the possibilities of replacing the conventional steel material by composites in the field of automobile. Wee ton et al describe the possibilities of composites used to replace the steel leaf spring as well as steel drive shaft. The advanced composite materials such as graphite, carbon, Kevlar and glass with suitable resins are widely used because of their high specific strength (strength / density) and high specific modulus (modulus / density). The first application of composite drive shaft to automotive was the one developed by Spicer U-joint divisions of Dana Corporation for the Ford econoline van models in 1985.

Drive shafts for power transmission are used in many applications, including cooling towers, pumping sets, aerospace, structures, and automobiles. In metallic shaft design, knowing the torque and the allowable service shear stress for the material allows the size of the shaft's cross-section to be determined. Beard

more also states the potentials of composites in structural applications. Conventional steel drive shafts are manufacture in two pieces to increase its fundamental natural bending frequency. The conventional assembly of drive shaft is made up in two pieces and joined together by u-joints due to which the overall weight of the assembly is increased. The composite drive shaft has advantages like considerable weight reduction, symmetric composite assured the dynamic balance of increasing operating speed, electrically non conductive, custom end fitting considerations, vibrations and harshness (NVH), long fatigue life and also it reduce the bearing & journal wear.

M.A.K. Chowdhuri, R.A. Hossain,[1] They studied. The basic requirements considered here are torsion strength, Torsional Buckling and bending natural frequency. An optimum design of the draft shaft is done, which is cheapest and lightest but meets all of the above load requirements. Progressive failure analysis of the selected design is also done. Also, composite materials typically have a lower modulus of elasticity. As a result, when torque peaks occur in the driveline, the driveshaft can act as a shock absorber and decrease stress on part of the drive train extending life. Dinesh et al. [2] They Designed composite drive shaft for wheel drive automobile by using genetic algorithm technique for E-glass/epoxy, high strength carbon/epoxy and high modulus carbon/epoxy composite with objective of minimization of weight of the shaft which was subjected to torque transmission, torsional buckling and natural bending frequency.

For automotive applications, the first composite drive shaft was developed by the Spicer U-Joint division of Dana Corporation for Ford econoline van models in 1985 [3].When the length of a steel drive shaft goes beyond 1500 mm, it is manufactured in two pieces to increase the fundamental natural frequency, which is inversely proportional to the square of the

length and proportional to the square root of the specific modulus. The nature of composites, with their higher specific elastic modulus, which in carbon/epoxy exceeds four times that of aluminum, enables the replacement of the two-piece metal shaft with a single-component composite shaft which resonates at a higher rotational speed, and ultimately maintains a higher margin of safety Rastogi [4] implemented a FEA approach to design and analyze a composite drive shaft with its couplings in different conditions. Rangaswamy et al. [5] optimized and analyzed a one-piece composite drive shaft using genetic algorithm and ANSYS. They found that the use of composite materials lead to the significant reduction in weight compared to steel drive shaft.

Table 1 Physical Properties

S.NO	Property	Notation	Value
1	Ultimate torque	T	3500 N-m
2	Maximum speed of the shaft	N	6500 rpm
3	Maximum diameter of the shaft	D	50 mm
4	Length of the Drive shaft	L	1500 mm

Table 2 Materials of Drive shaft and their mechanical Properties

MECHANICAL PROPERTY	STAINLESS STEEL	Glass/Epoxy	Carbon/Epoxy
YOUNGS MODULUS	210Gpa	39 Gpa	177 Gpa
SHEAR MODULUS	80Gpa	3.8 Gpa	7.6 Gpa
SHEAR STRENGTH	370Mpa	89 Mpa	83 Mpa
DENSITY	7700Kg/m3	2100Kg/m3	1600Kg/m3

For Drive Shafts Stainless steel was mainly used because of its high strength. But this stainless steel shaft has less specific strength and less specific modulus. Stainless steel has less damping capacity. Because of its higher density of molecules of stainless steel, its weight is very high. Because of increase in weight fuel consumption will in increase, the effect of inertia will be more. Because of increase in weight of the propeller shaft we are replacing the stainless steel with the composite materials, which are very less weight when compared to that of stainless steel. The cost of composite materials is less when compared to that of stainless steel.

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The E-Glass/Epoxy and Carbon/Epoxy materials are selected for composite drive shaft. Since, composites are highly orthotropic and their fractures were not fully studied. The factor of safety was taken as 2 and the fiber volume fraction as 0.6.

Stacking Sequence of composite material [0/45/90/-45/0]

The term stacking sequence refers to the schematic arrangement of fibres within the composite material. As the initial self-constraint was size of the shaft, the number plies were restricted to 5 numbers and with 5 plies we can make wide different range of stacking sequences and many sequences were considered and the best one is presenting in the paper. Among various sequences considered the best one would be [0/45/90/-45/0]. Following figure shows arrangement of plies.

They also reported that the fiber orientation of a composite shaft strongly affects the buckling torque. Kumar [6] performed an optimum design and analyzed a composite drive shaft for automobile application using a genetic algorithm approach.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM

The fundamental natural bending frequency of drive shaft for passenger cars, small trucks, and vans should be higher than 6,500 rpm to avoid whirling vibration and the torque transmission capability of the drive shaft should be larger than 3,500 Nm. The drive shaft outer diameter should not exceed 100 mm due to space limitations.

Figure 1 Stacking Sequence of composite Plies

ANALYSIS OF DRIVE SHAFT

Assumptions the shaft rotates at a constant speed about its longitudinal axis. The shaft has a uniform, circular cross section. The shaft is perfectly balanced, i.e., at every cross section, the mass centre coincides with the geometric centre. All damping and nonlinear effects are excluded.

Since model is not complicated one and it is modelled, meshed and analysed in Ansys itself. Hexa Mesh is made for better result and 4071 elements made with fine mesh size. The regular FEA procedure is followed and obtained results were plotted and compared.

Figure 3 meshed modal

Figure 2 hexagonal or brick elements

Figure 4 constrained model

After meshing model is constrained with fixed support at one end and other end torsional load is applied for torsional analysis and no load is given for model analysis. Various results obtained in Analysis were shown in next session.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Torsional analysis of Drive shaft

As discussed in the previous session for this analysis one end constrained with zero degrees of freedom and at another end torque of 3500 N-m is applied. Vonmiseses stress, Vonmiseses strain and shear stresses with in the shat at loaded condition for stainless steel, Glass epoxy and Carbon Epoxy are as below.

Vonmisesstress

Figure 5. Vonmises stress distribution in Steel, Glass Epoxy and Carbon-Epoxy Drive shafts

Vonmises strain

Figure 6 Vonmises strain distribution in Steel, Glass Epoxy and Carbon-Epoxy Drive shafts

Shear Stress Distribution

Figure 7 Shear stress Distribution in Steel, Glass Epoxy and Carbon-Epoxy Drive shafts

Figure 8 Comparison of characteristics of drive shaft with different material

From the above graph it is evident that from rigidity point of view stainless steel can be replaced with carbon and only disadvantage in glass epoxy having more displacement under similar loading conditions i.e. it has less torsional rigidity compared with carbon epoxy.

Modal analysis of drive shaft

In modal analysis natural frequencies and mode shapes are obtained by using Ansys and compared. First five mode shapes for each material are shown below.

Steel dive shaft

Figure 9 First five mode shapes of Steel drive shaft

Figure 10 First five mode shapes of Glass Epoxy drive shaft

Figure 11 First five mode shapes of Carbon Epoxy drive shaft

Figure 12 Comparison of natural frequencies of different material drive shafts

The above comparison graph shows that natural frequencies of composite materials are far below the stainless steel and theoretically it is not possible to replace the material but from the literature even if composite material having half of natural frequency of steel it is replaceable. Even in natural frequency point of view carbon epoxy is best suitable material for drive shaft.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions are drawn from the current work

- ❖ From figure 8 carbon-epoxy material with 5 plies of stacking sequence [0/45/90/-45/0] having similar rigidity i.e shear stress distribution, but bit more displacement.
- ❖ From figure 5 it is clear that carbon epoxy have good vonmises stress distribution among the others.
- ❖ From figure 12 natural frequencies of composite materials are far below the stainless steel
- ❖ Even if composite material having half of natural frequency of steel it is replaceable. in natural frequency point of view carbon epoxy is best suitable material for drive shaft.

- ❖ From above factors two piece stainless steel automobile drive shaft can be replaced with single piece carbon-epoxy material drive shaft with 5 plies of stacking sequence [0/45/90/-45/0]

REFERENCES

1. Chowdhuri M.A.K., Hossain R.A., "Design Analysis of an Automotive Composite Drive Shaft", 'International Journal of Engineering and Technology', Vol. 2(2), 2010, pp.45-48
2. Dinesh D., Anand Raju F., "Optimum design and analysis of a composite drive shaft for an automobile by using genetic algorithm and ansys", 'International Journal of Engineering Research and applications', vol. 2, Issue 4, July 2012, pp. 1874-1880
3. P.K. Mallick, S. Newman. Composite materials technology. Hanser Publishers. pp. 206-10, 1990.
4. N. Rastogi. Design of composite drive shafts for automotive applications. Visteon Corporation, SAE technical paper series 2004.2004-01-0485
5. T. Rangaswamy, S. Vijayrangan. Optimal sizing and stacking sequence of composite drive shafts. Mater. sci., Vol11
6. A.J. Kumar. Optimum design and analysis of a composite drive shaft for an automobile. Master's degree thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Balking Institute of Technology, Sweden, 2007.

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